

HIGHER ORDER FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES

Renato Barboni and Paolo Gaudenzi
(Dipartimento Aerospaziale Università di Roma La Sapienza
Via Eudossiana 16 00184 Roma (Italy))

ABSTRACT

A higher order deformation theory is developed in order to analyze static and dynamic behaviour of composite plates. The assumed displacement field allows to account for 3-dimensional effects, such as interlaminar shear stress and strain effects, on response parameters (maximum displacements, stress field, eigenfrequencies). Based on this deformation theory a class of finite elements is generated for one and two-dimensional structural elements. Triangular finite elements models are developed for the laminated plate at different orders of the theory. Numerical results concerning static and dynamic response problems are then compared with those obtained in the frame of classical laminate theory (CLT) and of three dimensional (3-D) elasticity theory.

INTRODUCTION

Interlaminar stress and strain components, e.g. the ones normal to the lamination surface, play an important role in continuum fiber composite mechanics. These components, which are usually neglected in the modelling of thin isotropic structures, may induce for highly orthotropic systems, such as composite laminates, considerable non conservative effects in structural static and dynamic problems. Moreover composite structures, in presence of materials with large Young modulus to shear modulus ratio, are susceptible to "thickness effects" and need, for adequate analysis, to account for correct transverse shear stress distribution. Therefore an accurate description of these phenomena with three-dimensional hypothesis for strain and stress is needed for a wide field of applications. In CLT a state of plane stress is assumed, transverse stress components are then neglected. On the other hand 3-D theories are cumbersome for more general applications. The approach here proposed, which accounts for the three-dimensional character of the stress field (Ref. 1,2), can be applied to many classical engineering problems concerning structures in which the geometry is essentially bidimensional.

THE ASSUMED DISPLACEMENT FIELD

In order to account for the 3-D character of the problem, displacement components are expanded in power series along the thickness direction:

$$u(x,y,z) = \sum_{m=0}^M z^m u_m(x,y) \quad v(x,y,z) = \sum_{n=0}^N z^n v_n(x,y) \quad w(x,y,z) = \sum_{k=0}^K z^k w_k(x,y) \quad (1)$$

This approach takes into account not only the transverse shear strains but also any order of approximation of the transverse shear strain variations along the thickness and therefore there is no need to use shear correction factor.

A CLASS OF FINITE ELEMENTS

The assumed displacement field (1) reduces the problem, from an analytical of view, from three to two dimensions; at this stage a two-dimensional FEM procedure is set up.

Being, for the displacement field

$$\{S(x,y,z)\}^T = \{u(x,y,z), v(x,y,z), w(x,y,z)\}$$

then

$$\{S(x,y,z)\} = [Z(z)] \{s(x,y)\}$$

is the matrix form of (1) with

$$[Z(z)] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & z & z^2 & \dots & z^M & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 & z & z^2 & \dots & z^N & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 & z & z^2 & \dots & z^K \end{bmatrix}$$

and

$$\{s(x,y)\}^T = \{u_0(x,y), u_1(x,y), \dots, u_M(x,y), v_0(x,y), \dots, v_N(x,y), w_0(x,y), \dots, w_K(x,y)\}$$

From the expression of the potential of the problem (Ref.1), it can be deduced that at least C^0 continuity requirement is needed for the shape functions of the finite element.

In the case of a bidimensional analysis a triangular finite element is developed assuming, over the element, quadratic shape functions $[N(x,y)]$ which relate every unknown contained in $\{s(x,y)\}$ to the nodal unknowns, collected in the vector $\{\delta\}$. The vertices of the triangle and the middle points of the sides are assumed as the six nodes of the element. For a monodimensional case (plate of infinite length in one direction) a 3-nodes beam-like finite element with quadratic shape functions is developed.

According to this procedure we have

$$\{s(x,y)\} = [N(x,y)] \{\delta\}$$

and

$$\{S(x,y,z)\} = [Z(z)] [N(x,y)] \{\delta\}$$

The strains are given by

$$\{\varepsilon\} = [D] \{S(x,y,z)\}$$

The stresses of the i th layer $\{\sigma\}_i$ are given by

$$\{\sigma\}_i = [C]_i \{\varepsilon\}$$

being $[C]_i$ variable layer by layer along z .

Equilibrium equations are derived following a variational approach; the number of equations obtained $(M+N+K+3)$ will be equal to the number of the unknowns (u_m, v_n, w_k) .

The local stiffness matrix $[K^e]$ and, respectively, the local mass matrix $[M^e]$ are derived as follows:

$$[K^e] = \int_{V^e} ([D] [Z] [N])^T [C] ([D] [Z] [N]) dV$$

$$[M^e] = \int_{V^e} \mu ([Z] [N])^T ([Z] [N]) dV$$

The global stiffness and mass matrix are then derived.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Consider a four-layer $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ simply supported square plate of width a , under static sinusoidal loading $q=q_0 \sin(\pi x/l) \sin(\pi y/l)$; the assumed set of material parameters is:

$$E_L/E_T = 25, G_{LT}/E_T = 0.5, G_{TT}/E_T = 0.2, \nu_{LT} = 0.25$$

The convergence of the procedure is assessed refining the mesh, for the different triangular finite element models, which correspond to different orders of the power series expansion of z .

Namely four finite element are developed; each model corresponds to the following assumed values for M, N and K :

- case A: $M=N=1, K=0$

- case B: $M=N=3, K=0$

- case C: $M=N=3, K=1$

- case D: $M=N=3, K=2$

In fig.1 maximum deflections w are reported versus the aspect ratio a/h . They are compared with those obtained with CLT and with the exact elasticity solution by Pagano-Hatfield (Ref.3). The first order theory (case A) corresponds to the Whitney-Pagano approach (Ref.4) with shear correction

factor $\chi = 1$. The higher order model (case D), is in better agreement with the exact 3-D elasticity solution than the first order one (case A); that is particularly true for low values of a/h . On the other hand for high values of a/h CLT is adequate to predict global deflections. Consequently taking into account interlaminar shear deformation is necessary (at least with the first order model) in the left region of the diagram of fig.1. The limits of this region, which are well established for isotropic

structures, depend, as far as laminated composites are concerned, also from the elastic properties. In fact these solutions are strongly affected by the degree of orthotropy of the material, as it can be seen in fig.2 in which maximum displacements of the $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ square laminate plate are reported versus E_L/E_T ratio, for CLT theory and for the present approach (case A and case D). In Table 1 and 2 displacements and stress components, calculated at different points of the structure, are compared with the exact values obtained by Pagano Hatfield (Ref.3) and with the approximate solution by Reddy et al. (Ref.5,6) and by Panda et al.(Ref.7). The results are in good agreement with the 3-D elasticity solution, with significant improvement with respect to the approximate solution by other authors. In fig. 3, 4 and 5 the values of σ_x , τ_{yz} and σ_z along z are reported for the first order (case A) and for the higher order models (case D). τ_{yz} is piecewise constant along z for case A and exhibits a parabolic behaviour for the case D. σ_z is due to the Poisson's effect for case A being $\epsilon_z=0$, and has parabolic behaviour for case D as reported in fig.5. For the cases A and B stresses are symmetric with respect to the $z=0$ plane, being w assumed for these cases as constant along z and being symmetric the laminate under concern.

Consider now a three-layer $(0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ)$ simply supported plate of infinite length in y direction and of width l in x direction, with the same assumed set of material parameters than the former example. For this structure the values of eigenfrequencies for the first four modes are determined. In fig.6 the eigenfrequencies are reported versus the aspect ratio l/h. First order shear deformation theory (case A) and higher order deformation theory (case B) are compared with classical laminate theory. In the range of low values of l/h, the eigenfrequencies calculated with CLT are strongly overestimated. Moreover the higher is the order of the mode the lower is the calculated eigenfrequencies with respect to CLT one. The differences between first order theory and higher order theory can attain values up to 7-8%.

CONCLUSIONS

In the former paragraph some samples of analysis are produced comparing results obtained adopting the present finite element approach here presented with well known exact solutions. A good agreement between numerical results and exact elasticity solution is obtained. The importance of the three-dimensional effect both for global response and for local aspects emerged in static and dynamic problems.

REFERENCES

1. R. Barboni, P. Gaudenzi: "Effetti degli sforzi interlaminari nei compositi " - Atti del IX Convegno AIDAA - Palermo 26-29 ottobre 1987 (in italian).
2. R. Barboni, P. Gaudenzi: "A finite element approach for composite laminated plate structural analysis"- Advancing in Composites- Int. Conference on Composite Materials- Milan 10-12 May 1988 , Proceedings Vol.II, pp.847-854.
3. N.J. Pagano, S.J.Hatfield "Elastic behaviour of multilayer bidirectional composites" - AIAA Journal, 10 (1972), pp.931-933.
4. J.M. Withney, N.N. Pagano "Shear deformation in heterogeneous anisotropic plates" - Journal of Applied Mechanics, 37 (1970), No.4, pp.1031-1036.
5. J.N. Reddy "A refined higher order theory for laminated composite plates" Journal of Applied Mechanics, (1984), pp. 745-752.
6. N.D.Phan,J.N.Reddy:"Analysis of laminated composite plates using a higher-order shear deformation theory" - Int. Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering, 21 (1985), pp.2201-2219.
7. Suresh C. Panda, R. Natarajari: "Finite element analysis of laminated composite plates" - Int. Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering, 14 (1979), pp.69-79.

Fig. 1

Figure 1: maximum deflection for a 4-layer $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ simply supported square plate of width a versus the aspect ratio a/h .

Fig.2

Figure 2: maximum deflection for a 4-layer $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ simply supported square plate of width a versus the ratio E_L/E_T , $a/h=6.25$.

Stresses for $a/h=4$; stacking sequence: $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$

	Exact el. sol.(3)	case A	case B	case C	case D	Reddy (5)
σ_x^* ($a/2, a/2, \pm h/2$)	0.720 -0.684	± 0.417	± 0.699	0.721 -0.677	0.723 -0.679	± 0.665
σ_y^* ($a/2, a/2, \pm h/4$)	0.663 -0.666	± 0.593	± 0.587	0.659 -0.663	0.651 -0.655	± 0.632
τ_{xz}^* ($0, a/2, 0$)	0.219	0.120	0.202	0.202	0.201	0.206
τ_{yz}^* ($a/2, 0, 0$)	0.292	0.174	0.254	0.254	0.254	0.239
τ_{xy}^* ($0, 0, \pm h/2$)	-0.047 0.046	-0.023 0.023	-0.038 0.038	-0.039 0.038	-0.038 0.037	0.044
degrees of freedom		45	81	90	99	

$$\sigma_x^*, \sigma_y^*, \sigma_z^* = \sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z h/q_0 (A/h)^2 \quad \tau_{xz}^*, \tau_{yz}^*, \tau_{xy}^* = \tau_{xz}, \tau_{yz}, \tau_{xy} h/q_0 (A/h)$$

TABLE 1

Displacements and stresses for $a/h=10$; stacking sequence: $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$

	Exact el. sol. (3) Pagano Hatfield	case A	case B	case D	Reddy (6)	Panda et al. (7)	CLT
$w^*(a/2,0,0)$	1.709	1.440	1.655	1.667	1.534	1.448	1.000
$\sigma_x^*(0,0,h/2)$	0.559	0.561	0.618	0.619	0.484	0.532	0.539
$\sigma_y^*(0,0,h/4)$	0.403	0.359	0.405	0.406	0.350	0.307	0.269

TABLE 2

Fig. 3

Figure 3: bending stress distribution along z for a $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ composite square plate; $a/h=4$, $x=y=a/2$.

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Figure 4: interlaminar shear stress distribution along z for a $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ composite square plate; $a/h=4$, $x=a/2$, $y=0$.

Figure 5: interlaminar normal stress distribution along z for a $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ composite square plate; $a/h=4$, $x=y=a/2$.

Fig. 6

Figure 6: natural frequencies versus length to thickness ratio l/h ; first four modes; $(0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ)$ cross-ply laminate plate of infinite length in y direction.

List of symbols

- $u(x,y,z)$ displacement component in x direction
- $v(x,y,z)$ displacement component in y direction
- $w(x,y,z)$ displacement component in z direction
- $\{S(x,y,z)\}$ vector of displacement components
- $u_m(x,y)$ generalized displacement component in x direction
- $v_n(x,y)$ generalized displacement component in y direction
- $w_k(x,y)$ generalized displacement component in z direction
- $\{s(x,y)\}$ vector of generalized displacement components
- $[Z(z)]$ assigned matrix of powers of z
- $[N(x,y)]$ shape function matrix
- $\{\delta\}$ vector of nodal displacement unknown
- $\{\varepsilon\}$ vector of first order strain
- $[D]$ matrix of derivatives which relates displacement components to first order strain components
- $\{\sigma\}_i$ vector of stress of the i th layer
- $[C]_i$ elastic stiffness matrix of the i th orthotropic layer
- $[K^e]$ local stiffness matrix
- $[M^e]$ local mass matrix
- V_e volume occupied by the element
- μ volume density
- q applied static load
- E_L Young's modulus of an orthotropic layer in the direction of the fibres
- E_T Young's modulus of an orthotropic layer in the direction normal to the fibres
- G_{TT}, G_{LT} transverse shear moduli of an orthotropic layer
- ν_{LT} Poissons' ratio for the directions parallel and normal to the fibres
- χ shear correction factor
- a width of the square plate
- h thickness of the plate
- f eigenfrequency
- l width of the plate of infinite length